

ISic3975

I.Sicily inscription 3975

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

exact provenance unknown; seen by Libertini (1921) in 'giardino dell'Episcopio'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 952

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334455

1. [— — — Ἄπολ]λονίου ²⁶Ἀπολλωνίου²⁶

2. ἐζώ [κ] ει

3. ἐνιαυτοῦς

4. ζ'.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334455

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 352

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 225 no.46

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3975. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4389489>